

Special Relativity and Rest Frame (x,t) Points Not Mapping 1-1 to (x',t')

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell. N.B. Dec. 4, 2024

In a number of previous notes, we argued that free particle quantum mechanics emerges from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, i.e. $t = t_0 + \hbar/E$ and $x = x_0 + \hbar/p$ yield the same A as x_0, t_0 . We also obtained this Lorentz invariant from $-EE + pp = -m_0m_0$ ($c=1$). The point we wish to make here is that even though the degeneracy in x', t' is present, a priori there is no reason to assign any physical reality to it because the inner product is a mathematical construct. In other words, a trajectory set (x, t) is usually not associated with an inner product. One might note that it is curious that an (x', t') and $(x' + \hbar/p, t' + \hbar/E)$ yield the same inner product with (p, E) , but a trajectory does not depend on the inner product definition, rather one has a set of (x, t) points in one frame and another set (x', t') in the moving frame where x' and t' are obtained using a Lorentz transform.

There is, however, a Lorentz transform which does govern a physical trajectory, namely: $-t't' + x'x' = -tt$. We have considered this before in connection with quantum mechanics, but in a slightly different manner. Here we argue that given a set of trajectory points $(x=0, t)$ in a rest frame, these do not map 1-1 to points satisfying $-t't' + x'x' = -tt$ (even though using only a Lorentz transformation does yield a 1-1 map.). The inner product equation, however, should be considered as representing physical trajectory points and so we argue that a degeneracy here means a physical degeneracy, i.e. the time and spatial uncertainty associated with motion (i.e. E and p). In general, in classical physics one wishes to have an equation linking x' and t' . Here one must introduce t as well. Now the Lorentz transform yields: $x' = vgt$ and $t' = gt$ so an equation of motion is $x' = vt'$ which is in fact the motion of the particle in the moving frame for $(x=0, t=0) \rightarrow (x'=0, t'=0)$. The $-t't' + x'x' = -tt$ equation, however, must also be respected and it is this equation which has multiple solutions. This equation is more general than $x' = vt'$. $x' = vt'$ requires no information about special relativity, whereas $-t't' + x'x' = -tt$ does and so this more general equation must be considered as well. As a result, we argue that there is no issue with the trajectory equation, $x' = vt'$, but that shifts in x', t' of B and B/v (B, B for a photon), must represent some different physical property. We note that in both the rest mass and photon cases, the shifts may be represented consistently using special relativistic variables through \hbar/E and \hbar/p and suggest that these uncertainties or fluctuations are linked with interactions, not trajectory motion as demonstrated in the 2-slit interference experiment for which an incident photon moves in a straight line (classical trajectory), but interacts with both slits. As the interaction occurs, one long follows a classical trajectory.

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

In previous notes, we have argued that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((1)) \quad \text{i.e. } A \text{ for } t_0, x_0 \text{ is the same as for } x_0 + \hbar/p \text{ and } t_0 + \hbar/E \quad ((2))$$

We have also argued that ((1)) may be obtained from the Lorentz invariant: $-EE + pp = -momo$ ($c=1$).

A main point we wish to make is that the Lorentz invariant or dot product is a mathematical property and does not necessarily govern physical results. In other words, one might dismiss the degeneracy of A as a curiosity. After all, in classical physics one deals with trajectories $x(t)$. A give (x,t) in one frame maps to an (x',t') in a moving frame and ((1)) is always respected and so the degeneracy of A may be dismissed as a non-issue.

We argue, however, that there is a Lorentz invariant that one cannot dismiss, namely:

$$-t't' + x'x' = -tt \quad ((3))$$

This follows from applying the Lorentz transformation to points $(x=0, t)$ in a rest frame, obtaining:

$$X' = g vt \quad \text{and} \quad t' = gt \quad \text{where} \quad g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((4))$$

((4)) gives rise to two equations:

$$x' = vt' \quad (\text{which does not require special relativity for its derivation}) \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$-t't' + x'x' = -tt \quad ((5b))$$

Now, $x' = vt'$ with $(x=0, t=0) \rightarrow (x'=0, t'=0)$ yields a set of distinct (x', t') points defining a trajectory in the moving frame. Each one of these may be thought of as arising from a different $(x=0, t)$ point using ((4)). This gives 1-1 mapping between the two frames, but ((5b)) does not if one divides it by t' to obtain:

$$-t' + v x' = -t/g(v) \quad ((6))$$

If one considers ((6)) for one t value at a time, one sees that the usual $x' = gvt$ and $t' = gt$ is a solution, but another is:

$$x' + B/v \quad \text{and} \quad t' + B, \quad \text{where } B \text{ is an arbitrary constant.} \quad ((7))$$

Now ((7)) violates $(x=0, t=0) \rightarrow (x'=0, t'=0)$ because $x' = B/v$ and $t' = B$ are solutions of ((6)) even for $t=0$ ($x=0$). In other words, $x' = B/v$ and $t' = B$ violates a Lorentz transformation. Is this a problem? We argue that it is not, if one considers B/V and B to be fluctuations. $(x=0, t)$ maps to (x', t') according to a Lorentz transformation and defines the physical trajectory. ((7)) shows that there exists something beyond this physical trajectory. Thus B/v and B are not shifts from one physical trajectory to another, but rather represent an uncertainty fluctuation. This suggests that even though there is no uncertainty in the trajectory in the moving frame, i.e. $x' = vt'$, there is some uncertainty which exists for x' and t' . This begs the question: What could such uncertainty be if it is not in the trajectory?

We argue that B/v and B may be written in terms of special relativistic variables (for a particle with rest mass), namely $1/p$ and $1/E$. In other words, this prescription could be used in all frames. What happens in the case of photon which does not have a rest mass?

In such a case: $E=p$ ($c=1$) and $-t't' + x'x' = -tt+xx$ must be used where $x=ct$ or

$-t't' + x'x' = 0$ Then $-t'+x'=0$ so $t'+B$ and $x'+B$ is still a solution, where $c=1$. This is again equivalent to using $1/E$ and $1/p$, so there is consistency.

This still does not answer the question regarding the physical meaning of fluctuations in x' and t' which have nothing to do with a trajectory. We suggest that if one uses E and p (i.e. \hbar/E and \hbar/p), then this might have something to do with interaction hits as E and p are interaction variables. In other words, interactions do not follow the center-of-mass trajectory which is what one sees in 2-slit interference experiments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue for free particle quantum mechanics using the Lorentz invariant $-t't' + x'x' = -tt$ (particle with rest mass and a similar expression for a photon), because we argue that these equation describes a physical trajectory as well as $x'=vt'$. The latter shows 1-1 mapping with (x,t) states, but the former allows for two solutions, x',t' and $x'+B/v$ and $t'+B$ (in the case of rest mass) and $x'+B$, $t'+B$ for a photon with $c=1$. Given that the trajectory is well defined in the moving frame, we suggest that $B/v, B$ (or B, B for a photon) should represent some kind of impulse-interaction fluctuation. We note that in both the rest mass, m_0 , and photon cases, one may write the fluctuations or x',t' uncertainties as $\hbar/p, \hbar/E$. This seems to be consistent with the 2-slit interference experiment for which the incident photon has a classical trajectory, but near the slits starts to interact with both of them (and the classical trajectory is lost with the x',t' fluctuations taking over and governing the interaction physics).